

1 **Angiotensin and adrenomedullin expression changes are a signature component of the TE**
2 **differentiation program.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophoblast (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of
9 angiotensin and adrenomedullin as central lineage commitment factors in embryonic stem cells of the
10 human embryo.

11 Citations

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13 A., Edholm, D. and Aspenström, P., 2007. Angiotensin regulates endothelial cell migration during
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